

The MOSAiC webODV: Interactive online data exploration, visualization and analysis

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In the frame of the **M-VRE** (The MOSAiC virtual research environment, <https://mosaic-vre.org>) project we have set up a **webODV** application, to serve data from the arctic **MOSAiC** (<https://mosaic-expedition.org>) expedition.

webODV is deployed at AWI's computing center under <https://mvre.webodv.cloud.awi.de>.

MOSAiC data have been retrieved from the long-term archive Pangaea (<https://pangaea.de>).

To get the most out of the data with **webODV**, we have harmonized, aggregated and compiled the datasets into different separated and interdisciplinary data collections.

webODV is operated interactively in the browser via the mouse and keyboard (no programming), it's fast, efficient and easy to use for exploring, visualizing, analyzing, downloading data, creating map projections, scatter plots, section plots, surface plots and station plots and many more.

webODV supports the FAIR data principles and analyses and visualizations are fully reproducible using our so-called "xview" files that can be shared among colleagues or attached to publications. We provide real-time sharing, full author traceability and downloadable lists of all the DOI's used in the analysis or the respective .bib or .ris files including all citations. Extensive documentation is available at <https://mosaic-vre.org/docs> as well as video tutorials at <https://mosaic-vre.org/videos/webodv>.

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